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Review Article

Mirroring The Mystery By Mapping Out The Molybdenum From *Vigna Unguiculata*

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ABSTRACT

Micronutrient are important growth promoting elements for human being. More than two billion of the global population are malnourished .For developing countries like India, micronutrient malnutrition among the people of every age is very common. The review article discusses the essential of molybdenum and its effect on the human body and we break down why it is important to health and the extraction of little known trace element of molybdenum from *Vigna unguiculata*. Molybdenum needed by the body in tiny amount ,but this is enough to participate in many vital processes, without it toxic accumulate in the body, amino acids are not absorbed, DNA is not processed. The rich source of molybdenum is *Vigna unguiculata*. *Vigna unguiculata* belongs to the family of Fabaceae, which is commonly known as cowpeas. The phytochemical are carbohydrates, proteins, fats ,vitamins, minerals ,soluble and insoluble dietary fibres with varying amount of glycosides ,alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, polyphenols, saponins, vignalin, oleanolic acid acetate and sitosterol β -Dglycosides. Molybdenum is the target compound to be extracted from the solid matrix of *Vigna unguiculata* by using soxhlet extraction method and various identification tests are performed .Object for identification such as compound and analysed sample are discussed in great detail the finding are significant and indicate the essential of molybdenum for human. So,this review summarised holistic approach required to develop sustainable “REDUCE THE MICRONUTRIENT MALNUTRITION OF MOLYBDENUM”

INTRODUCTION

Micronutrient are needed by the body in very small amounts. However, their impact on a body health

are critical and deficiency of micronutrient can causes severe and even life threatening conditions. Many of the deficiency are preventable through

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consumption of a healthy diet containing diverse foods. In this review we discussed briefly about the micronutrient of molybdenum. Molybdenum is an essential mineral in the body. A molybdenum deficiency is extremely rare and has been reported in infants with a genetic disorder in which the mineral cannot be used and therefore cannot break down sulphites, which may lead to brain damage and seizures. A deficiency has also been in people receiving intravenous nutrition in which supplement molybdenum was not added. Signs of deficiency include seizures, death in infants, irregular heart rate in adults. Molybdenum co-factor deficiency is noted genetic condition for deficiency of molybdenum. It is rare condition characterized by brain dysfunction that worsens over time. Molybdenum co-factor deficiency causes brain abnormalities, delay childhood death, intellectual disabilities, seizures, opisthotonus and lens dislocation. The rich source of molybdenum is *Vigna unguiculata*, which is commonly known as cowpeas, black eyed pea, crowderpea, southernpea. Cowpeas may have several health benefits including digestion, immunity, sleep, weight loss, heart health. It belongs to fabaceae family that can be either annual or perennial herb. Cowpeas can be climbing, trailing, erect, prostrate, creeping it depends on the cultivator, the leaves are compound, with two asymmetrical side leaflets and one terminal leaflet are symmetrical. The seeds have different characteristics like shape, size, colour, texture. The shape of the seeds are usually kidney shaped, wild cowpea are very small. Cowpea seeds can be white, cream, green, red, brown, black or combination of colour and its texture has a smooth or rough coat and can be speckled, mottled or blotchy. Molybdenum is the target to be extracted from the solid matrix of *Vigna unguiculata* by Soxhlet extraction method. Soxhlet extraction is a continuous process of

extraction with a hot organic solvent and also removing the chemical constituent from the seeds of *Vigna unguiculata* and various identification tests are performed to flavonoids, soluble and insoluble dietary fibres.

Taxonomical Classification

Division	Angiosperem
Class	Magnoliopsida
Kingdom	Plantae
Subclass	Rosids
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	Vigna
Species	unguiculata

Synonyms

English	Cowpea
Hindi	Lobia, Kulathi, Kurathi
Sanskrit	Mahamasah, Rajamasah
Tamil	Kaattulundu, Karamani
Marathi	Alasunda
Telugu	Alasandalu, Kaaraamanulu
Kannada	Alasande
Malayalam	Vellapayar
Urdu	Kulthi

Distribution:

India, Central America, China and Africa. In India mostly cultivated, in Uttar Pradesh, Chotanagpur, Assam and in southern states of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh.

Plant Profile:

Herbaceous annual with twining stems varying in erectness and bushiness. Leaves trifoliolate, petioles 2.5 to 12.5 cm long. Central leaflet hastate, 2.5 to 12 cm long, smooth, lateral leaflets irregular. Flowers in axillary racemes on stalks 15 to 30 cm long. Pod pendulous, smooth, 10 to 23 cm long with a thick curved beak and 10- to 15-seeded. Seeds 4 to 8 mm long, 3 to 4 mm broad, variable in size and colour.

Leaves

Compound leaves with three leaflets

Flowers

Bisexual flowers with five fused sepals and five free petals, usually growing in pairs at the ends of long stalks

Pods

Long and cylinder pods that can grow 20 to 30cm long and can contain six to 13 seeds

Seeds

Kidney shaped seeds that can be white, cream, green, red, brown, and black or various combination

Seed Coat:

Seeds can have a smooth or rough coat, and be speckled, mottled, or blotchy.

Importance of Molybdenum in Human Body
Molybdenum is an essential trace mineral that helps the body in many including

1. Processing proteins and genetic material

Molybdenum helps the break down process proteins and genetic material like DNA

2. Breaking down drugs and toxins

Molybdenum helps breakdown drugs and toxic substance that enter the body.

3. Preventing toxins from building up

Molybdenum helps the body get rid of harmful sulfites and prevents toxins from building up in tissues

4. May help with esophageal cancer

Studies have shown that a deficiency in molybdenum may play a role in the higher incidence of esophageal cancer in populations consuming food grown in soil low in this mineral.

Molybdenum Deficiency

Molybdenum also acts as the cofactor that is required in order to metabolize sulfur amino acids, nitrogen-containing compounds. There are compounds in DNA and RNA that have a variety of functions. The lack of molybdenum does not appear in healthy individuals, but there is a specific metabolic consequence known as molybdenum co-factor deficiency which results from an inadequate amount of molybdoenzymes in the body. The molybdenum toxicity of humans is small, owing to the rapid excretion of this mineral in urine. The people with a very rare genetic condition called co-factor molybdenum deficiency, the body is not able to use molybdenum as a result of this disorder. It can cause seizures and severe brain damage that usually leads to death within days after birth of infants.

Causes of molybdenum:

There is a relatively rare lack of molybdenum in humans due to the fact that there are very low level of this mineral required by the body. Molybdenum is required for a number of fundamental processes in the biological system, e.g. metabolism of amino acids from sulfur and elimination of some compounds. There are some possible causes of molybdenum deficiency are

Insufficient dietary intake:

If a person's diet is very low in molybdenum-rich food, he or she may suffer from Molybdenum deficiency. Legumes, whole grains, leafy vegetables, nuts, and organ meat are good sources of molybdenum.

Malabsorption:

Molybdenum may be hard to absorb from the diet in people who suffer from some health conditions that are affecting their absorption of nutrients.

Amino Acids:

A diet excessively high in sulfur-containing amino acids (methionine and cysteine) can increase the body's demand for molybdenum. If there is insufficient dietary intake to meet the increased demand, it may be capable of producing a molybdenum deficiency.

High intake of molybdenum antagonists:

Some dietary compounds, such as tungsten or some sulfite-derived food additives, can have a negative influence on the absorption and use of molybdenum in the body. Molybdenum depletion may be associated with consuming a high amount of these compounds.

Metabolism Deficiencies:

In fact, as molybdenum-dependent enzymes need these cofactors to function properly, a deficiency in essential nutrients like copper or iron can have an indirect effect on metabolism. Genetic

Disorders:

In rare cases, individuals with inherited genetic disorders that affect molybdenum metabolism, such as molybdenum co-factor deficiency, may be at risk of molybdenum deficiency.

Malnutrition:

There may be risks of various nutrient deficiencies, including molybdenum deficiency, for persons who are malnourished or have limited access to a variety of food.

Risk Factors:

Molybdenum deficiency is crucial to maintaining optimal health. Molybdenum, an essential trace mineral, plays a vital role in various physiological process within the body. While molybdenum deficiency is relatively rare, certain factors can increase the risk of developing this deficiency. One of the primary risk factors for molybdenum

deficiency is a diet lacking in foods that are rich in this mineral. Molybdenum is found in various food sources such as legumes, whole grains, nuts, and leafy green vegetables. Individuals who consume a highly processed or restricted diet may not be obtaining adequate amounts of molybdenum, thus increasing their risk of deficiency. Certain medical conditions and medications can also contribute to molybdenum deficiency. Gastrointestinal disorders that impair nutrient absorption, such as Crohn's disease or Celiac disease, can interfere with the body's ability to absorb molybdenum from the food sources. Individuals who have undergone bariatric surgery or have had a portion of their intestines removed may also be at an increased risk of molybdenum deficiency due to reduced absorption capacity. It's important to note that while these risk factors may increase the likelihood of developing a molybdenum deficiency, it does not necessarily mean that individuals will experience symptoms or complications. Regular monitoring and consultation with a healthcare professional are essential for identifying and addressing any potential deficiencies.

Symptoms:

The symptoms do not appear to be well documented due to a limited number of reported cases. The body's need for molybdenum is also relatively low, given that it requires very little in the form of trace amounts. However, if a deficiency occurs, there can be several symptoms that are not associated with molybdenum deficiency but may also appear in addition to the symptoms of another nutrient deficit or normal health conditions. The following symptoms may occur as a result of molybdenum deficiency like Fatigue, a broad feeling of tiredness or weakness. Weakness: Reduced muscle strength and endurance.

Rapid heartbeat:

An increase in heart rate may be observed in some people who are not adequately Molybdenum deficient.

Headaches:

Some cases of persistent or severe headaches have been observed.

Nausea:

The feeling of nausea or a sick stomach, loss of Appetite: a reduction in desire to eat or diminished appetite

Cognitive Symptoms:

Neurological symptoms, such as confusion and disorientation, may occur in severe cases.

Diagnosis:

There may be difficulties in the diagnosis of molybdenum deficiency in human beings due to it's a fairly rare condition and symptoms are not specifically related to such deficiency. A combination of treatments, such as a doctor's history, physical examinations, and laboratory tests is often used by healthcare professionals for the determination of molybdenum deficiency. In order to diagnose molybdenum deficiency, the following steps shall be taken:

1. Clinical assessment:

The healthcare provider starts by verifying the patient's health records and performing an examination of his or her body. They'll look at a patient's nutrition and any health conditions that are currently in place, as well as the presence of specific symptoms that can be indicative of malnutrition.

2. Blood tests:

It is possible to determine molybdenum levels in the body through blood tests. In particular, blood levels of molybdenum can be measured by a healthcare professional. These tests are not widely available and, in most cases, do not constitute part of the regular blood work.

3. Assessment of symptoms:

A molybdenum deficiency may be suspected in the presence of some symptoms, e.g. fatigue, weakness, and neurological problems. Given the overall health status of a patient, it is important to take these symptoms into account.

4. Dietary assessment:

To determine if a patient is at risk of molybdenum deficiency as a result of the consistently low intake of molybdenum-rich foods, healthcare professionals may ask patients about their dietary habits.

Treatments:

1. Changes in diet:

The most common and generally recommended way of addressing the lack of molybdenum is to change foods that have a higher content of molybdenum. The recommended sources of molybdenum include legumes, such as beans and lentils; whole grains, leafy vegetables, nuts, and organ meat. It is possible that increasing the intake of these foods will lead to increased levels of molybdenum in the body.

2. Molybdenum supplements:

Health care professionals are encouraged to prescribe mineral supplements for patients who have a severe deficiency or when diet changes do not work. Molybdenum supplements can be obtained in various forms, like molybdenum trioxide or molybdenum aspartate. A healthcare provider shall determine the prescribed dose and form of molybdenum supplementation.

3. Monitoring:

Periodic blood molybdenum levels monitoring can help resolve the deficiency when you start to alter your diet or supplement with molybdenum. Based on the needs of each individual, healthcare professionals will develop a suitable follow-up schedule.

4. Preventive Measure:

You should eat a balanced diet including foods that are high in molybdenum, such as beans, whole grains, leafy vegetables, nuts, and meat. Excessive intake of sulfur amino acids can increase molybdenum demand, so be careful. Ensure a balanced intake of methionine and cysteine. Control gastrointestinal disorders and other conditions that may restrict nutrient absorption, as these could be contributing to a lack of molybdenum. Periodic assessments, early identification of deficiencies in nutrients such as molybdenum, and timely intervention if necessary, may be useful for the assessment of nutritional status.

Method of Extraction of Molybdenum From Cowpeas :

Soxhlet extraction is a general and well established technique. This technique is based on exhaustive the extraction of organic compounds , in a soxhlet system by an organic solvent . The seeds of cowpeas needs to be crushed, using a mortar and pestle to provide a greater surface area the material should be sufficient to fill the porous cellulose thimble. The solvent is added to a round bottom flask, which is attached to a soxhlet extractor and condenser on a isomantle. The crushed seeds of cowpeas are loaded into the thimble which is placed inside the soxhlet extractor the side arm is lagged with glass wool .The solvent is heated using isomantle and well begin to evaporate, moving through the apparatus to the condenser. The condensate then, drips into the reservoir containing the thimble. Once the level of solvent reaches the siphon it pours back into the flask and the cycle begin again.The process should run for a total of 7 days .Once the process has finished ,the ethanol should be evaporated using a rotary evaporator leaving a small yield of extracted crushed seed of cowpeas in the glass bottom flask

Chemical Constituents:

Generally plant contains Carbohydrates (56-67%), Proteins (20.5-31.7%), Fats (1.14-3.03%)

vitamins, minerals, soluble and insoluble dietary fibers with the varying amount of glycoside, alkaloids, flavanoids, tannis, saponins, vignalin, the saponincy aglycone part of which belong to the oleanane series of triterpenoids identified as soyasapogenol B. Twenty varities of cowpeas with the following proximate composition :dry matter 87-94%,crude protein 24-33%,ether extract 1-2%,crude fibre 2-5%,and ash2-5% were analysed. The flours of cowpeas contains important source of protein 24.30-26.33%,ash 2.71-3.64%,and starch 50.99-51.33% were amylase was found in the range of 16.72-19.15%.

Dry matter	93.3
Crude protein	20.91
Ether extract	2
Crude fiber	3.4
Ash	4.1
Nitrogen free extract	62.89

ESSENTIAL MINERALS (mg/100g)

AMINO ACID(%)

Calcium	126	alanine	18.7
Magenisum	51	arginine	14.3
Phosphrous	53	Aspartic acid	27.8
Pottasium	431	cysteine	3.6
Sodium	4	Glutamic acid	43.5
Iron	1.10	glycine	9.5
Zinc	1.01	histidine	4.5
Ascorbic acid	2.5	isoleucine	5.3

Medicinal Uses

The seeds are edible and used as the source of dietary protein. They also used to strengthen the stomach and destroy the worms in stomach. The plant is used in measles, smallpox, adenitis, burns and sores. Decoction or soup is used in affection of the liver and spleen, intestinal colic, in leucorrhoea and menstrual disorder, urinary discharges. It is used as astringent, appetizer, Antipyretic, Diuretic, laxative, aphrodisiac, diuretic, anti-hyperglycemic, antinociceptive,

galactogogue and liver tonic. It exhibits thrombolytic, antisickling, antioxidant and free radical scavenging activities. Also exhibits Antibacterial activity against both the Gram positive and gram negative organism. Useful in jaundice, epilepsy, constipation.

Pharmacological Studies

Anthelmintic Activity

Vigna Unguiculata Walp. Seeds are coarse powdered and exhaustively with hot solvent (Soxhlet) extraction by ethanol and maceration

with chloroform water I.P. Five concentration (10-100 mg/ml) of ethanolic and aqueous extracts were studied for anthelmintic activity by using *Edriluseginiae* earthworms. Both aqueous and ethanolic extracts showed paralysis and death of worms in concentration (10-100mg/ml) dependent manner. Alcoholic extract of *Vigna Unguiculata* Walp showed significant activity than aqueous extract. Piperazine citrate (10mg/ml) and distilled water were included in the assay as standard drug and control respectively. The result showed seeds of *Vigna Unguiculata* Walp possessed potential anthelmintic activity.

Antimicrobial Activity

Aqueous and ethanolic extracts of seeds of *Vigna unguiculata* Walp were studied for antibacterial activity and was tested against Gram positive bacteria, *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* by agar well diffusion method. Different concentrations (100 µg/ml, 200µg/ml and 300µg/ml) of the extracts were incorporated into the wells. Both the extracts showed concentration dependent activity against the microorganisms investigated. The results showed the highest positive antibacterial activity with an inhibition diameter of 22mm in case of aqueous extract of 300µg/ml concentration, against the Gram negative bacteria; *Escherichia coli*. The *E.coli* species were found to be more sensitive than that of the *Bacillus subtilis*. The aqueous extract exhibited more antibacterial activity against both the Gram positive and Gram negative organisms than that of the ethanolic extract.

Antioxidant activity

In screening of antioxidant activity of the methanolic extracts of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* Walp) .seeds. Phenolic compounds present in the extracts showed the antioxidant and antiradical properties when investigated using a linoleic acid

peroxidation model, FRAP, ORAC and TRAP assays, as well as DPPH, hydroxyl, nitric oxide and superoxide radical scavenging activity. The HPLC analysis of the cowpea extracts showed the presence of neochlorogenic acid, chlorogenic acid and caffeic acids. The results indicated that methanolic extract of the cowpea resembled in the aforementioned activities those from other leguminous seeds and pulses.

Antinociceptive activity

Antinociceptive activity was examined through the observe of decrease in abdominal constrictions in intraperitoneally administered acetic acid-induced pain model in mice. Administration of methanol extract of beans results in dose dependent and significant decreases in blood glucose levels in glucose-loaded mice. The tests for antinociceptive activity results, that the methanolic extract decreases the number of abdominal constrictions by 30.0, 33.3, 36.7, and 43.3%, respectively in all above four doses. This study concluded that the beans can be a good source for alleviating pain and for lowering blood sugar in diabetic patients.

Antimicrobial activity

The antimicrobial activity of *Vigna unguiculata* Walp seed oil was investigated against five Gram positive bacteria (*Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Sarcinalutea*, *Salmonellatyphi* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and four Gram negative (*Escherichia coli*, *Shigelladysenteriae*, *Shigellasonnei*, *Shigellashiga*) and four fungi (*Penicilium spp.*, *Mucor spp.*, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillusfumigatus*). Oil at the concentration of 400 µg/disc showed the highest activity against *Sarcinalutea* (19±0.1 mm) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (16±0.1 mm). Oil is active against the three tested fungi namely *Penicilium spp.*, *Mucor spp.* and *Candida albicans* but showed no sensitivity against *Aspergillusfumigatus*.

Antidiabetic activity

The seed oil of *Vigna Unguiculata* Walp was investigated for its anti-diabetic activity against alloxan monohydrate induced diabetes in rats. Levels of blood glucose, TC, TGs, LDL, ALT, AST and ALP decreased and HDL increased in alloxan induced diabetic rats after treatment with 200 mg/kg barbati seed oil for 21 days. The study reported that the seed oil of cow pea may be very useful for the improvement of the complications of diabetes.

Hypocholesterolemic activity

The seeds of *Vigna unguiculata* Walp was investigated for its Hypocholesterolemic activity in wistar rats. Rats were grouped and fed a high fat diet with 20% Bombay (BO), 20% MI 35 (MI), 20% Cowpea extract, 20% Dawala (DA) in comparison with 20% casein (HFD). Serum total cholesterol, non-HDL cholesterol, triacylglyceride and glucose concentrations were analyzed. Serum lipids and glucose concentrations in cowpea fed rats were significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) than HFD. Therefore, raw cowpea produced significant hypolipidemic and hypoglycemic effects in Wistar rats.

Antiviral and antifungal activity

The *Vigna unguiculata* Walp seeds were examined for the presence of various proteins and amino acids with antiviral and antifungal potency. The two proteins, designated α - and β -antifungal proteins according to their elution order from the CM-Sepharose column, were capable of inhibiting human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) reverse transcriptase and one of the glycohydrolases associated with HIV infection, α -glucosidase, but β -glucuronidase was not repressed. The ability of the proteins was also demonstrated in order to retarding mycelial growth of a variety of fungi, and α -antifungal protein being proved more potent in most cases. β -Antifungal protein was highly

active in only one instance. Both antifungal proteins had low cell-free translation-inhibitory activity.

Antisickling activity

Natural plant products have been used in Nigerian folk medicine in the management of sickle cell anemia by inhibiting sickling. This work was therefore aimed at investigating the Antisickling potential of the ethanol seed extract of *Vigna unguiculata* used in the Nigerian herbal medicine with a view of proposing an effective herbal recipe for the management of sickle cell disease. Sickling inhibition test, sickling reversal test and polymerization test were carried out using standard methods. The results of the antisickling test showed that *Vigna unguiculata* had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher antisickling effect than Hbss control. The result of the polymerization showed that, extracts significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased delayed time before polymerization at 50, 25 and 12% concentrations compared to the control. From the results, the extracts *Vigna unguiculata* have shown to be therapeutically beneficial in the management of sickle cell disease and thus it is strongly recommended by this study to be developed into supplements for the management of sickle cell disease.

Thrombolytic activity

Inquisition with methanolic extract of *Vigna unguiculata* Walp (seeds) was carried out to determine the thrombolytic potential of this plant. Five different concentration (2mg/ml, 4mg/ml, 6mg/ml, 8mg/ml, and 10mg/ml) of methanolic extract was used to evaluate thrombolytic activity. In-vitro Thrombolytic model was used. The plant showed significant clot lysis, i.e. concentrations 12.01 ± 1.50 , 16.48 ± 2.31 , 24.88 ± 1.49 , 31.24 ± 0.68 , 40.33 ± 3.64 at 2mg/dl, 4mg/ml, 6mg/ml, 8mg/ml, 10mg/ml respectively, while the standard (streptokinase) and negative control (distilled

water) showed 58.41 ± 3.71 and $2.56 \pm 1.23\%$ clot lysis respectively. It is clear that *Vigna unguiculata* Walp (seed) methanolic extract showed thrombolytic activity significantly while comparing with standard.

CONCLUSION

Medicinal plants have the ability to synthesize a wide variety of chemical compounds that are used to perform important biological functions. The above plant contains enormous phytochemical constituents. The extensive survey of literature revealed that *Vigna Unguiculata* Walp, is an important medicinal plant with diverse pharmacological spectrum. The pharmacological studies reported in this review confirm the therapeutic value of *Vigna Unguiculata* Walp. The plant possesses various activities such as anthelmintic, antibacterial, antioxidant, free radical scavenging, antinociceptive, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, hypocholesterolemic, antiviral, antifungal, antisickling and thrombolytic activity. Hence, this plant provides a significant role in the prevention and treatment of a disease. The importance of micronutrient and role of molybdenum in human body are noted.

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